

Development of a bioreactor and volumetric bioprinting protocol to enable perfused culture of biofabricated human epithelial mammary duct and endothelial constructs

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Abstract

Tissue function depends on the 3D spatial organization of cells, extracellular matrix components, as well as dynamic nutrient gradients and mechanical forces. Advances in biofabrication technologies have enabled the creation of increasingly sophisticated tissue models, but achieving native-like tissue maturation post-fabrication remains a challenge. The development of bioreactors and microfluidic systems capable of introducing dynamic culture platforms and controlled mechanical and biochemical stimulation for biofabricated tissue analogues is therefore imperative to address this. In this technical note, we introduce a multi-step pipeline to fabricate, seed and perfuse geometrically complex hydrogel constructs with quality control protocols through the computational analysis of confocal multispectral 3D imaging data for each step of the process. Employing ultra-fast volumetric bioprinting, chips with tunable channel architectures were fabricated. Furthermore, an autoclavable and transparent perfusion bioreactor inspired by open-source designs was developed to enable controlled, long-term perfusion (up to 28 days) and real-time monitoring of cell behavior. As proof-of-concept, employing this pipeline, we fabricated a human mammary ductal model and an endothelialized vessel on-a-chip, demonstrating the compatibility of the platform with epithelial and endothelial cell lines, and investigated the effect of dynamic culture on tissue-specific cell organization. Dynamic perfusion underlined the influence of mechanical stimulation on cell organization and maturation. Various chip architectures, capable of recapitulating tissue-specific features (*i.e.* lobules) were printed, enabling the mono- and co-culture of human mammary epithelial and endothelial cells. Our pipeline, with the accompanying protocols and analysis scripts presented here, provide the potential to be applied for the dynamic culture of a wide range of tissues.

Key words: Biofabrication, volumetric bioprinting, perfusion bioreactor, organ-on-a-chip

35 1. Introduction

36 It has long been recognized that tissue function relies on the 3D spatial organization of cells, matrix components and
37 growth factors^{1,2} as well as dynamic nutrient and oxygen gradients and mechanical forces applied onto and by cells³.
38 While *in vivo* animal models are valuable in biomedical research to study cell behavior in a native environment, their
39 predictive capacity is greatly limited, due to interspecies differences⁴. Existing human *in vitro* models, on the other
40 hand, lack complexity to faithfully recapitulate tissue function^{5,6}. To combat these issues, the field of biofabrication
41 has made great strides on making increasingly more architecturally complex tissue models^{7,8}. However, while
42 biofabrication allows the precise control over cell and biomaterial patterning, full tissue maturation, essential for
43 proper biological function, can often not be achieved solely by depositing cells into their desired location and must
44 occur through measures taken post-fabrication⁹. Therefore, many bioreactors^{10,11} and microfluidic systems^{12,13} have
45 been developed to provide flow or other (mechanical) stimuli to different tissue constructs to improve cell viability¹⁴,
46 migration¹⁵, differentiation¹⁶, morphogenesis¹⁷ and nutrient- as well as oxygen transport^{14,18}.

47 In this technical note, we introduce a novel and versatile methodology to converge volumetrically bioprinted¹⁹ chip
48 constructs with microfluidics to enable the fabrication of a geometrically complex and perfusable bioprinted hydrogel
49 construct. We provide landmarks on how to seed the chips and computationally assess printing accuracy, seeding
50 efficacy and cell alignment, as well as organization. We combine the bioprinted chips with the rapid in-house
51 production of an autoclavable and transparent CNC milled perfusion bioreactor to enable dynamic cell culture. This
52 bioreactor, inspired by available open-source designs²⁰, allows for perfusion, as well as imaging access from top and
53 bottom, enabling the real-time monitoring of cells within bioprinted chips. It further enables direct tissue access, for
54 additional manipulation or subsequent analysis, a feature often lacking in organ-on-a-chip systems^{21,22}.

55 As a proof of concept, we demonstrate the compatibility of our platform with both epithelial and endothelial cells,
56 ensuring applicability across multiple tissue types. Our proposed biofabrication pipeline is applied to modelling human
57 mammary gland (MG) and endothelial tissues, which rely heavily on their intricate 3D architecture and cellular
58 organization - features that conventional 2D and 3D culture systems cannot faithfully mimic^{23,24}. Here, using the high-
59 speed volumetric bioprinting (VBP) approach, we can recapitulate ductal geometries with a widely used,
60 biocompatible hydrogel (gelatin methacryloyl; gelMA) to direct cellular organization of mammary epithelial cells
61 (MCF10A) and endothelial cells (human umbilical vein endothelial cells; HUVECs). We demonstrate that healthy
62 human mammary epithelial cell lines react to flow with more recapitulative organization and polarization than non-
63 flow controls, mirroring in part the biological impact of milk flowing through the duct system that has a crucial role
64 in the upkeep of secretion and production of milk²⁵⁻²⁸. We further leverage VBP's freedom of design to generate more
65 complex ductal architectures by introducing small, curved protrusions throughout the printed channels, mimicking to
66 some extent the lobular units of the mammary gland. The resulting chip, together with additional surface features
67 produced by the VBP process, can be used to influence cell alignment and invasion into the surrounding hydrogel. By
68 further introducing a second channel to our chip construct seeded with endothelial cells, we demonstrate the possibility
69 of creating complex, multicellular tissue-like models within a compliant hydrogel and combined with dynamic
70 perfusion. Such a dynamic culture platform could be further exploited to exert spatiotemporal control over bioactive
71 cue presentation, in the case of the present breast model, for instance, to introduce hormonal stimulation, essential for

72 mammary tissue homeostasis. With this novel pipeline, we present an open-source workflow that can enable better
73 mimicry of complex cellular processes that cannot easily be studied with current human *in vitro* models. The
74 methodology and technological solutions, as well as computational methods, provided here are aimed at facilitating
75 access and adoption of on-a-chip and bioreactor systems and help researchers address key bottlenecks in consistent
76 cell seeding and perfusion culture within their custom-designed models. In addition, all design specification and CAD
77 files for the bioreactor and cell seeding aid devices are provided in an open science framework (OSF) repository.
78 Herein, by combining the power of volumetric bioprinting with an adapted perfusable bioreactor and relevant
79 computational analysis workflows, we have engineered a vascularized human breast model system that could, in the
80 future, be applied to study human mammary gland biology in health and disease. Through this proof of concept, we
81 open the door for the translation of this platform towards other target tissues that can benefit from dynamic culture or
82 for advanced disease modeling.

83

84 **2. Results and discussion**

85 **2.1 Chip design and production**

86 The field of microphysiological systems has become one of the most advanced in the creation of complex *in vitro*
87 models, as they enable the microscale recapitulation of functional tissues and organs^{29,30}. In particular, devices such
88 as organ-on-a-chip platforms have been developed for a myriad of biomedical applications, from disease modeling,
89 toxicity testing, and the study of multi-tissue interactions³⁰. The most rudimentary method for modeling tubular
90 tissues in these devices involves casting the desired biomaterial around a removable needle to create simple, straight
91 channel-on-chip designs (Fig.1(a)). While efficient when dealing with stiff materials, developing these molded chips
92 with soft, biocompatible hydrogels presents some limitations. In this study, gelMA was selected as the base chip
93 material because of its wide adoption in the tissue engineering and biofabrication fields, given its tunability and
94 inherent resemblance to native extracellular matrix components³¹. When molding chips from gelMA using the needle
95 approach, however, cell seeding attempts showed very low efficiency. The number of cells that remained within the
96 channel long enough to attach was low and highly variable between samples, and large amounts of cells were observed
97 passively floating out of the chip altogether. As a visual demonstration, the same tendency was observed when
98 injecting fluorescent beads within these straight, horizontal channels, which were also highly prone to elicit air bubble
99 formation when plugging the chip closed (Fig.1(b),(c)). Consequently, a U-shaped chip design was developed in which
100 the cells were not able to float out of the chip but rather were forced inside the duct by gravity (Fig.1(d)). Channel
101 diameters ranged from 500-1000 μm depending on the experiment, which is well within the range of macro tubular
102 native structures, and, pertaining to our proof-of-concept, is also in the range of normal mammary duct diameters (~
103 750 μm at ~4 mm distance to the nipple)³². Since this curved design could not be easily casted with a needle-pull-out
104 approach, we turned to 3D printing technologies, which more easily enable the fabrication of complex, out-of-plane
105 structures, and have been widely used for the production of organ-on-a-chip devices³³. In this study, we employed
106 volumetric bioprinting to enable the shaping of gelMA hydrogels into these more complex chip structures, given its
107 high printing speed, design freedom, and compatibility with hydrogels and living cells¹⁹. Light-doses between 180-

108 260 mJ/cm² (printing time = 20-30 s) enabled the fabrication of open channels. A comparison between the original
109 computer-aided-design (CAD) files and the 3D reconstructions of printed chips - obtained through light sheet
110 microscopy - via nominal actual comparison in CloudCompare showed a strong resemblance to the reference model
111 (Fig.1(e,g) and Suppl.Fig.1(a)). Overall, printed chips were slightly larger than reference models, likely due to
112 swelling of the hydrogel post-printing. The average deviation from the original CAD model was 1.94 ± 2.96 % within
113 acceptable ranges (± 7 % nominal vector deviation) with lowest deviations in X and Y direction (± 5 %) and highest
114 deviations in Z direction (= longitudinal axis of the printer vial; ± 20 %), occurring at low frequencies, only in specific
115 locations of the print (Fig.1(i-k)). For instance, at the edges of the chip and the inlets of the duct, over-polymerization
116 could be observed. We compared the over-polymerized areas to the predicted light-intensity accumulations provided
117 through Apparite software and found that all printing deviations were in line with the predicted 3D model-specific
118 accumulation of light intensities in these regions (Fig.1(f,h)). The correlation between local light-intensity
119 accumulation and print accuracy is therefore a useful tool that can be employed to locally optimize CAD models to
120 improve overall printing outcomes. Together, these results demonstrate that our technique allows for the production
121 of chips with curved, hollow, and perfusable channels that accurately resemble the original CAD model and facilitate
122 cell retention upon seeding.
123

124 **2.2 Seeding of volumetrically bioprinted chips**

125 With the possibility to create complex channel structures using VBP, a consistent cell seeding strategy, and a method
126 to assess seeding efficiency were also established. Cell seeding to form a confluent layer along the whole channel
127 surface can be achieved by turning the chip in regular intervals [20]. Therefore, a rotating station was implemented to
128 enable the automated rotation of multiple chips simultaneously. The sample holder was designed to fit chips mounted
129 inside bioreactors as well as chips mounted within multi-well plates (Fig.2(a), Suppl.Fig.2(a)). As a proof-of-concept,
130 MCF10A cells were chosen as a well-characterized epithelial cell line reflecting normal human mammary epithelium.
131 Initial testing of the seeding station using 30 million MCF10A/mL showed that rotation of the chips allowed for an
132 even seeding around the whole channel surface (Fig.2(b) left, suppl. video 1), as opposed to non-rotated samples
133 where cells predominantly stuck to the bottom of the channel (Fig.2(b) right). Cell and channel segmentation were
134 performed in Imaris software and cell coverage of the seeded channels were calculated from a custom-built python
135 script (Fig.2(c), Suppl.Fig.1(b)), which is provided in our open-source repository³⁴.

136 Optimal seeding conditions were tested on 6% w/v gelMA as this provided an optimal stiffness (Young's modulus of
137 8.4 ± 2.6 kPa) to keep printed channels open. Seeding was also optimized for human umbilical vein endothelial cells
138 (HUVECs) mixed with mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), to demonstrate the applicability of the developed platform
139 to endothelial structures, given the open challenge of creating and studying vascularized tissue models *in vitro*. Both
140 MCF10A and HUVECs/MSCs did not attach well on gelMA-only chips (coverage = 49.54 ± 16.17 %). Therefore,
141 poly-L-lysine, L-Dopamine and collagen-1, which have previously been reported to improve endothelial and epithelial
142 cell attachment in microfluidic devices, chip systems and on gel surfaces including gelatin-based hydrogels³⁵⁻³⁸ were
143 investigated. Furthermore, different cell seeding densities were tested (7.5-60 million cells/mL) (Fig.2(d-i), Suppl.Fig.

144 2 (b)). For MCF10A, coating with poly-L-lysine (PLL) led to significantly better cell attachment (coverage = $88.23 \pm$
145 14.5%) than on non-coated chips (coverage = $48.59 \pm 22.18 \%$) or collagen-1 coated chips (coverage = 49.43 ± 31.7
146 $\%$) (Fig.2(d, e)). Low (7.5 M cells/mL) as well as high (60 M cells/mL) MCF10A seeding densities yielded a high
147 channel coverage (83.82-88.39 %) within a week after seeding (Fig.2(g)), suggesting that the initial seeding density
148 does not significantly influence the channel coverage within the chosen range. Notably, when working with lower cell
149 densities (<60 M cells/mL), sometimes gaps in cell coverage could be observed, which could be closed by employing
150 a second round of cell seeding 3 days after the initial seeding (Suppl.Fig.2(c), red circles). In order to reduce the
151 necessary amount of cells and to avoid possible cell clumping sometimes seen when using high cell densities (60 M
152 cells/mL) (Suppl.Fig. 2 (c), yellow circles), a density of 30 M MCF10A/mL and double seeding, which is in a similar
153 range as reported for similar breast-on-a-chip models [29], was chosen to obtain uniformly seeded channels. Regarding
154 channel endothelialization through HUVEC/MSC seeding, channel coverage was lower (coverage = 66-77 %) compared to MCF10A (83.82-88.39 %) when seeded on PLL and collagen-1 coated channels. Therefore, we tested
155 the combination of collagen-1 and PLL, as well as a fibrin coating, which has previously been successful in retaining
156 endothelial cell attachment³⁹. While fibrin coating did not yield an improved cell coverage, a 1:1 mix of collagen-1
157 with PLL resulted in 81 % cell coverage, although an increased sample size will be necessary to confirm whether this
158 improvement is significant. This coating formulation was subsequently used for all endothelial seeding experiments
159 (Fig.2(h,i)). Our data demonstrates that different cell types might require different coatings for optimal attachment.
160 As both mammary epithelial cells as well as endothelial cells are in their native environment exposed to a basal
161 lamina^{40,41}, future research will be directed at mimicking the basal lamina by the use of laminin-containing coating
162 materials.
163
164

165 **2.3 Development and fabrication of a perfusion bioreactor accessible for imaging**

166 To provide additional functionality to previously reported bioreactors²⁰, we developed our own bioreactor design
167 to allow for the perfused culture of ductal cell seeded hydrogel chips. We introduced a thin glass coverslip (0.1 mm
168 thickness) at the bottom of the device to enable cell monitoring using inverted microscopy. Additionally, to prevent
169 the hydrogel-based chips from drying out and enable the use of different media types outside and inside the channel,
170 we included two medium chambers placed at the sides of the central housing for the chip. A lid with two entry ports
171 to plug in fluidic tubing was designed to permit perfusion starting from the top of the hydrogel-based constructs
172 (Fig.3(a)). The lid was equipped with guiding extensions, which keep it in place so that the tubing inlets are accurately
173 positioned on top of the channel inlets. The bioreactor is closed with 3D printed clamps applying pressure of the lid
174 onto an O-ring embedded in the bottom part of the bioreactor to prevent leakage. These clamps can easily be slid off
175 to enable access to the cultured tissue for the addition of cells or post-culture analysis.

176 Bioreactors were initially 3D printed from polyethylene terephthalate glycol (PETG) using fused deposition modeling
177 (FDM) (Fig.3(b)). However, the small access window in the lid (formed by a cover slip) did not provide enough visual
178 access to the chip, impeding the installation of tubing for perfusion. Further, if used more than once, chips in 3D
179 printed bioreactors were prone to infections, likely due to the layered microtopography providing an extensive surface

180 area and roughness for bacterial adhesion⁴². Therefore, after optimizing the dimension and features for perfusion of
181 the printed chips, final reusable bioreactors were produced from autoclavable transparent polycarbonate via CNC
182 milling, yielding transparent bioreactors, which allowed for infection-free long-term tissue culture (Fig.3(c)). All
183 bioreactor parts were autoclaved before each use. No reduction in transparency could be observed over time (5-10
184 autoclaving cycles). Critical for our bioreactor design was the ability to perfuse from the top due to the advantages of
185 a curved channel design for cell seeding (See section 2.1 *Chip design and production*). Therefore, tubing inlets had to
186 be incorporated into the bioreactor lid, preventing the use of a glass slide to retain visual access to the chip. The chosen
187 transparent polycarbonate as a bioreactor material allowed us to insert tubing from the top, while maintaining visual
188 access and providing additional sterility, due to the possibility to be autoclaved.

189

190 **2.4 Perfusion influences mammary epithelial cell organization and barrier function**

191 After seeding, hydrogel-based chips were transferred to the bioreactor after cells had enough time to attach firmly (3
192 days). When needles were inserted into the chip to initiate perfusion, the chips frequently ruptured at the interface
193 between the soft hydrogel and hard metal (data not shown). Therefore, flexible fishing tubing was used, forming a
194 smoother transition between tubing and gel. This soft tubing was able to adapt to the shape of the chips rather than
195 disrupt it by following the curvature of the duct inlets. The tubing was inserted through the holes of the bioreactor lid
196 and into the chip until the curvature of the channel gave a palpable resistance. Tubing was secured from moving by
197 adding 3D printed tubing clips (Fig.3(d)). At the beginning of the culture period, chips were initially perfused at low
198 flow settings (80 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$) for the first two days to prevent not yet fully attached cells from detaching. After initiation of
199 perfusion some cell detachment was observed. However, cell detachment was minor, and cells quickly repopulated
200 the resulting gaps. Under dynamic perfusion (400 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$), cyclic, pulsatile channel expansion and recovery of the
201 bioprinted hydrogel lumen were observed, leading to a decrease/increase of channel width of up to 4% in response to
202 the pulsatile flow (Fig.4(a,b); Suppl. video 2,3). This demonstrates that chips made from 6% w/v gelMA, as opposed
203 to traditional PDMS chips⁴³, are highly compliant, similar to native tubular and flow-subjected tissues, a crucial
204 characteristic for the ability to respond to and transmit mechanical forces to cells [30]. The use of a compliant hydrogel
205 is therefore advantageous in the context of microfluidics as it enables the study of tangential, axial, and circumferential
206 shear stresses, which are known to affect endothelial barrier function, cell alignment, morphology, proliferation,
207 migration, and remodeling⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶. Flow-induced mechanical forces have also been shown to play a role in epithelial
208 organization, barrier function, and migration⁴⁷⁻⁵¹. Indeed, after one week of perfusion, MCF10A cells started to
209 infiltrate the surrounding gelMA (Fig.4(c), right), forming sprouts around the channel of an average length of $195 \mu\text{m}$
210 $\pm 68 \mu\text{m}$ and up to $338 \mu\text{m}$ in length, as opposed to statically cultured chips, where no sprouting was observed over
211 the culture period (Fig.4(c)). After two weeks of dynamic culture (400 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$), cell-free and statically cultured and
212 perfused cell-seeded channels were injected with FITC-inulin and leakage was assessed over time via live imaging to
213 assess epithelial barrier function. As expected, due to the absence of barrier-forming cells, FITC-Inulin leaked out of
214 cell-free channels leading to a 2.9-fold increase of FITC signal outside the channel. Furthermore, FITC-inulin leakage
215 from statically cultured MCF10A chips was observed (1.97 fold increase of FITC signal outside the channel), while

216 perfused channels mostly retained FITC-Inulin inside the channel lumen (1.2 fold increase of FITC signal outside the
217 channel) for the whole duration of imaging (> 1 h), demonstrating an increased epithelial barrier function induced by
218 flow (Fig.4(d,e); Supplementary video 4, Suppl.Fig. 1(c)), as has been previously demonstrated for a variety of
219 epithelial cell types⁴⁷⁻⁵¹. Subsequently, chips were stained for breast epithelial markers, CK14 (basal), CK8/18
220 (luminal), E-cad (breast epithelial) as well as DAPI (nuclei) and Phalloidin (membranes) and imaged using
221 multispectral 3D imaging⁵². Imaging data indicated that the application of flow led cells to properly organize and
222 polarize into a CK14 positive outer cell layer and a CK8/18 positive luminal cell layer, while non-perfused chips
223 displayed a more random organization (Fig.4(f,g)). Indeed, quantification of cells covering the inner edge of the duct
224 using a custom python script (Suppl.Fig. 1 (d)) confirmed that 91.14 ± 11.57 % of the cells were positive for K8/18
225 in perfused channels, while only 47.04 ± 2.59 % were K8/18 positive on non-perfused channels. Further, a trend was
226 observed where 77.95 ± 2.73 % of the cells covering the inner edge of the perfused duct were not only K8/18 positive
227 but also followed by an outer layer of K14 positive basal cells, displaying correct luminal-basal organization
228 (Fig.4(h,i)). This demonstrates that the application of flow through our bioreactor design is able to guide cellular
229 organization of epithelial ductal models post-printing through mechanical stimulation and delivers an indication of
230 the important role that flow plays in the organization and polarization of mammary epithelial cells, an important factor
231 influencing functional maturation⁵³. While the above mentioned changes in cell barrier function and organization
232 could already be observed after two weeks, we were able to keep samples in perfused culture for up to four weeks
233 without leakage of the system, infections or noticeable deformation of the matrix material. Future research will have
234 to elucidate the exact timing of cellular processes induced by flow stimulation, as well as optimal timing and intensity
235 of flow in these long-term perfusion cultures but is out of the scope of this technical note.

236

237 **2.5 Guiding cell alignment and invasion through micro- and macro-topographical features**

238 During printing and seeding optimization, we frequently observed striped topographies in printed chips on their x,y-
239 plane (Fig. 4 (c)). This has previously been explained: if static, laser light projections using a coherent light source are
240 delivered onto a non-rotating vial, straight microfilaments and channels can be formed in the printed object, due to
241 laser speckle patterns⁵⁴. This results in the formation of finely striated prints upon rotation of the resin vat during the
242 VBP process⁵⁵. It should be noted that, if a smooth surface is required, there are protocols in place to remove striations
243 post-printing entirely^{55,56}. However, since cell alignment is known to be influenced by the microscale surface
244 topographies, such as grooves and fibers⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹, we investigated how the intrinsic striation elicited by VBP could be
245 leveraged to guide cell alignment in our printed channels. We observed that, when printing the chip construct vertically
246 (as shown in Fig 5) both endothelial and epithelial cells aligned concentrically along the printed channel following
247 concentric striations created during the printing process (Fig.5(a)). Notably, cell alignment could be steered by
248 changing print orientation, and by printing the chips in a horizontal orientation striations were aligned along the
249 longitudinal axis of the channel (Fig.5(b,c)). Upon seeding, segmentation of the cells covering the channel surface
250 revealed that this change in the directionality of striations significantly influenced cellular alignment for both MCF10A
251 and HUVECs, which, when seeded on horizontally printed chips, aligned along the longitudinal axis of the channel

252 (Fig.5(d,e); Suppl.Fig.1(e)) displaying a more native-like orientation⁶⁰. However, it should be noted that this change
253 of print orientation made it more difficult to correctly resolve and print open channels. Nominal actual comparison
254 between CAD model and printed chips showed that over polymerization in horizontally printed chips could occur
255 along the channel, reducing the channel lumen dimensions (Fig.5(f)) in line with the increased expected light
256 accumulation in this area (Fig.5(g)). Given the limited contrast between in- and off-target voxels, this resulted in prints
257 that are highly susceptible to small variations in the bioresin reactivity, for instance, due to batch-to-batch variation in
258 the hydrogel formulation. Knowing of the increased likelihood of over polymerization within the channel, only chips
259 with 1 mm duct diameter in the CAD design were printed horizontally, accommodating for the expected reduction in
260 channel diameters and leading to a higher success rate in printing chips in a horizontal orientation. While these
261 microtopographies instructed cellular alignment, previous results of Nelson et al., on mammary epithelial cells have
262 demonstrated the guidance of epithelial cell migration behavior through instructive geometries. Mammary epithelial
263 cells preferably branched into the surrounding tissue at local maxima of convexity²⁴. To investigate whether this
264 observation could be applied to our printed constructs, we therefore introduced small lobular units along the duct, to
265 provide maximum convexity for the MCF10A cells in our platform (Fig.5(h-j)). Indeed, together with the striations,
266 the newly introduced lobules lead to MCF10A invasion into the surrounding tissue. This invasion reached depths of
267 $189 \pm 57 \mu\text{m}$ and was significantly higher in those convex lobular regions than in ductal regions ($79.9 \pm 20.2 \mu\text{m}$)
268 (Figure 5 (k,l) and Supplementary Figure 3 (a)). Furthermore, cell invasion was led by K14 positive basal cells
269 followed by K8/18 positive luminal cells (Fig.5(k-l)), confirming that the introduction of macro-topographical features
270 such as convexity provides sufficient instruction for the cells to invade their surroundings and possibly initiate
271 branching morphogenesis. Conclusively, our data demonstrates that VBP can be used to introduce micro- and
272 macroscale geometrical cues which guide cellular organization and tissue invasion.

273

274 **2.6 Increasing model complexity: development of a multicellular chip platform**

275 Having set up a workflow to generate perfused epithelialized or endothelialized ductal models, we explored different
276 strategies to increase cellular heterogeneity, to potentially enhance tissue maturation and biomimicry of the desired
277 tissues in future studies.

278 A key element of organ-on-a-chip systems, is the ability to recreate multicellular or multi-tissue interactions²⁹. To
279 demonstrate this potential application of our chip platform we first showed the possibility to print more than one
280 channel and seed different cell-types in each one, in this case demonstrating the creation of a vascularized mammary
281 duct model as a proof-of-concept. To facilitate targeted cell seeding in this two-channel system, we adjusted the design
282 to include an x-shaped curvature (Fig.5(m)), since printing channels in close proximity ($200 \mu\text{m}$) initially made it
283 challenging to inject cells into their designated channel. By increasing the distance between the inlets while
284 maintaining a small channel separation, we improved the precision of cell seeding with multiple cell types (MCF10A
285 and HUVECs/MSCs). Chips were cultured in 1:1:1 MSC:HUVEC:MCF10A media under static conditions. Channels
286 were injected with their respective culture medium, and epithelial and endothelial cells remained in their respective
287 separate compartments. The smallest vascular-to-epithelial channel distance achieved was $200 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig.5(n)), and at

288 this distance, no branching or sprouting towards the other cellular compartments was observed. Future studies should
289 focus on the optimization of the inter-channel spacing to ensure the desired cellular interactions can take place within
290 the developed chip platform. Alternatively, the introduction of stromal cells directly into the printed chip could be
291 employed to enhance intercellular interactions between seeded channels, and to better simulate native tissue
292 composition and organization. Since VBP is a mild, contactless process, it allows the incorporation of cells and larger
293 cellular units such as organoids sensitive to stresses from other printing methods^{19,61,62}. Here, we demonstrated the
294 feasibility of printing the developed chip platform in the presence of MSCs (Supp. Fig. 4 (a)). These cells represent a
295 stromal component that can be tailored to fit tissue-specific requirements. Cells remained viable (>90% viability) for
296 a 2-week period (Supp. Fig. 4 (b)), and the mechanical properties of the printed chip remained constant during this
297 time (Supp. Fig. 4 (c)), suggesting that cell incorporation into the bioresin would not significantly affect the stability
298 of the chip.

299 The developed perfusable platform introduced in this study has the potential to enable the study of complex biological
300 processes in a reproducible, quality controlled fashion. Having established the possibility to produce more native-like
301 chip platforms, further modifications to the system could be introduced to target tissue-specific requirements such as
302 the introduction of materials that better mimic the ECM composition of the tissue of interest - such as granular⁶³,
303 ECM-derived⁶⁴ or dynamic, light-sensitive hydrogels compatible with the VBP process - or the introduction of
304 channel/cell-specific growth factors and/or hormones to induce a more physiological environment for cells to mature.

305

306 **3. Conclusions**

307 In this technical note, we presented a biofabrication pipeline including volumetric bioprinting of ductal chips, cell
308 seeding, perfusion bioreactor/platform development and instructions for perfused culture. We further provide five
309 different imaging-driven analysis pipelines addressing printing accuracy, cell coverage, cell alignment and construct
310 maturation. We provide open access to all CAD models needed for the fabrication of the chip, bioreactor, rotator and
311 perfusion platform, as well as all analysis scripts in our OSF repository³⁴. Our pipeline is set up to be easily adapted
312 for changes in the experimental setup (e.g. addition of a second channel or more complex geometrical cues) and,
313 therefore, has the potential to be translated to various ductal types of tissue such as kidney, gut, or the presently
314 demonstrated mammary duct and vascular applications. With these pipelines and analysis scripts we aim to contribute
315 to aiding the development of more advanced organ-on-a-chip models with clearly defined and accessible readout
316 parameters.

317 We applied our pipeline for the production of biomimetic chips using established epithelial and endothelial cell lines
318 and show that volumetric bioprinting delivers chips of high print accuracy. We demonstrate the influence of micro-
319 and macro-topographical features on cell alignment and invasion into the surrounding tissue and show that flow-
320 induced shear stress and repetitive stretching of our compliant hydrogel chips improve mammary luminal-basal
321 epithelial cell organization and barrier function.

322 Since the aim of this technical note was to provide a framework for the production and seeding of chip structures that
323 can be applied to various tissue types, we here restricted our biomaterial choice to gelMA and different materials for

324 channel coating. Tissue-specific changes in matrix composition could, therefore, be the subject of further investigation
325 and it has to be noted that cell behavior, like amongst others attachment, might differ across varying materials of
326 different stiffnesses. Future research aimed at improving model maturation could include steps, such as the
327 incorporation of additional stromal cell types, hormonal stimulation or changes in culture conditions, including
328 hypoxia⁶⁵. As a proof-of-concept, we predominantly used human cell lines throughout this technical note. However,
329 we envision that increased model maturity can be achieved by using more representative cell sources, for instance
330 human breast organoids^{66,67} or blood vessel organoids⁶⁸. We have demonstrated that our pipeline is compatible with
331 the use of organoids by seeding human mammary organoids onto our ductal chip structures and previous work has
332 demonstrated that organoids can also be incorporated into the volumetric bioprinting process with high viability⁶¹.
333 Through the incorporation of strategies to enhance tissue maturation and cellular interactions within our platform, this
334 work paves the way for the creation of more recapitulative organ-on-chip models that can bring about advanced disease
335 modeling applications in future studies.

336 **4. Methods**

337 ***4.1 Bioreactor fabrication***

338 Bioreactor designs were generated in Fusion360 and all CAD and CAM files can be found as editable STEP files and
339 as stl files in the OSF repository³⁴. Bioreactor iterations were 3D printed from white PETG (123-3D Filament Wit
340 1,75 mm PETG 1 kg (Jupiter serie)) at a layer height of 0.15 mm with ironing enabled for all top surfaces. The final
341 bioreactor design was milled from transparent and autoclavable 5 mm polycarbonate (kunststofplatenshop.nl;
342 polycarbonaat helder 5 mm) using a Sainsmart3040 CNC and end mills of different sizes (0.8 mm, 1 mm, 2 mm, 3
343 mm) suitable for soft plastics (Stepcraft; End mill set "low melting plastics" (11706)). As clamps were not in direct
344 contact with cells or printed chips, they were 3D printed from white PETG. To assemble the bioreactors, two
345 components of PDMS were mixed (Dow, SYLGARD™ 182 Elastomer kit) and pipetted into the gasket of the
346 bioreactor bottom. A 0.1 mm glass cover slide was stuck onto the PDMS to the bottom of the bioreactor. A 20x2 mm
347 silicone O-ring (Amazon.de; BGS O-Ring Assortment 3 – 22 mm diameter, PACK of 225 + 8044) was inserted into
348 the round gasket of the bioreactor lid. Bottom and lid of the bioreactor were connected using the clamps. Before use
349 of the bioreactor bottom and lid were autoclaved to ensure sterility.

350 ***4.2 Design and fabrication of cell seeding equipment***

351 Inspired by the gel flipper described by Kinstlinger et al.²⁰ a rotating station was designed. All parts needed to build
352 the rotator can be found in Supplementary table 1 and design files in the OSF repository³⁴. 3D printed parts were
353 designed in Fusion360 and printed from PLA (123-3D Filament zwart 1,75 mm PLA 1,1 kg (Jupiter serie)) on a Prusa
354 i3 MK3S at a layer height of 0.2 mm. To improve stability, support was added on both sides connected by aluminum
355 extrusions and a leadscrew. In the middle of the leadscrew a 3D printed holder was attached which fits both 15 cm
356 petri dishes and regular sized well plates (Suppl.Fig.1A). Along with that a stamp to mold PDMS inside 15 cm petri
357 dishes to hold up to 4 bioreactors per dish was designed. This setup allowed seeding of chips both already mounted

358 into bioreactors, as well as within well plates, when screenings of many conditions required seeding of many chips at
359 the same time. Well plates, as well as petri dishes, were sealed with parafilm before starting the flipping process, to
360 ensure sterility despite vibrations during the rotation process. In Arduino IDE, the arduino nano was programmed to
361 turn the dish holder by 90 degrees every 15 min. The script can be found in the OSF repository³⁴ .
362

363 **4.3 Hydrogel preparation**

364 GelMA (80 % degree of functionalization, synthesized as previously described ⁶⁹) was weighed under sterile
365 conditions and dissolved in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) without calcium and magnesium (PBS0) at 6% w/v and
366 mixed with photoinitiator lithium phenyl(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl)phosphinate, (LAP, Tokyo Chemical Industry,
367 Japan) at a final concentration of 0.1 % w/v. GelMA was kept in the dark at 37 °C until used. 1 mL or 2 mL of GelMA
368 were filled into 10 mm or 20 mm glass vials, respectively. Vials were closed with a silicone plug and GelMA was
369 allowed to thermally gelate in the dark on ice for 10 min.

370 **4.4 Chip fabrication and mounting**

371 The hydrogel-made chip structures were designed with Fusion360 and converted to printable STL files. Design files
372 can be found in the OSF repository³⁴. Chips were printed either horizontally (20 mm vials) or vertically (10 mm vials)
373 using a commercial volumetric bioprinter (Tomolite, Readily3D SA) at a light dose of 180-215 mJ/cm² from 6 %
374 w/v GelMA. Immediately after printing, uncured GelMA was washed away using warm PBS0 and chip channels were
375 thoroughly flushed with PBS0 and examined for openness of the channels. All chips were post cured in PBS with 0.1
376 % w/v LAP in the UV oven for 2 min. Subsequently, chips were either inserted into bioreactors or mounted into 24-
377 well plates. Chips were fixed in place in 24-well plate wells by spreading a thin layer of 10 % w/v GelMA onto the
378 bottom of the well before adding the chip and UV cross-linking it to the chip for 2 min.

379 **4.5 Assessment of print accuracy**

380 To assess printing accuracy, we stained our GelMA with Cy3.5 (Cy3.5-PEG-SH, Biopharma PEG Scientific Inc;
381 FL077003-5K) prior to printing. Using a custom-built light-sheet microscope we scanned the different chip versions.
382 Chips were segmented using Imaris and the 3D reconstruction exported to wrl-format. In Meshlab software, wrl files
383 were converted to stl format. Reference stl files and reconstructed files were aligned in CloudCompare using ICP fine
384 registration. Absolute deviations were calculated using cloud-to-cloud distance computation and exported to csv. In
385 R we calculated original point coordinates (Reconstructed_Coordinate + (C2M_signed_distanced*Nominal vector))
386 and subsequently percentage deviations which were back projected onto the reconstructed mesh as a scalar field
387 (Suppl.Fig.2A). Print deviations were further compared to the predicted light accumulations calculated automatically
388 by Apparite software (Readily3D), which estimates the light dose delivered in every voxel of the print, starting from
389 the cumulation of the 2D projections delivered at every angle of rotation of the vial during the tomographic printing
390 process. The light dose values are defined by the tomographic algorithms that govern the printing process and,
391 therefore, are known and can be accurately calculated by the printer's software.

392 **4.6 Coating of the printed channels within the chips**

393 Different coatings were applied to the chips depending on the intended cell types to be cultured in the system. Both
394 10 mM L-Dopamin (L-DOPA, Sigma Aldrich; 53587-29-4) and Poly-L-Lysine (PLL, Sigma Alrich) were injected
395 into channels and incubated for 30 min at 37°C before flushing channels with cold PBS0. For multimaterial coatings,
396 a 3 mg/mL collagen-1 solution (col-1; Corning, rat tail, CLS354236) was mixed with PLL and BME (Basement
397 Membrane Extract, Cultrex RGF BME type 2, R&D systems, 3533-005-02) to final concentrations of 2 mg/mL col-
398 1, 30 % v/v PLL, 1 % v/v BME. The mixture was injected into channels and incubated for 10 min at 37°C.
399 Subsequently, channels were flushed with ice cold 20 X PBS. For fibrin coatings, fibrinogen and thrombin were mixed
400 1:1 on ice to a final concentration of 2 mg/mL fibrinogen and 2 U/mL thrombin. The fibrin solution was injected into
401 channels and incubated at room temperature (RT) for 2 min before flushing the channels with ice cold PBS0. All chips
402 were rotated into all directions before flushing the coating out of the chips to ensure that the coating reaches all sides
403 of the channel.

404 **4.7 Cell expansion and culture**

405 MCF10A normal epithelial cells (ATCC CRL-10317™) were cultured according to manufacturers recommendations.
406 Briefly, MCF10A cells were seeded in T75 culture flasks and MCF10A medium (Advanced DMEM + 5 % v/v Horse
407 serum + 1 % v/v P/S + 20 ng/μL EGF + 0.5 μg/mL Hydrocortisone + 10 μM Forskolin + 10 μg/mL Human insulin
408 (Sigma 11061-68-0)) was added and refreshed once a week. Once confluent, cells were split at a 1:6 ratio.
409 For the vascular co-culture, GFP-HUVECs were cultured in cell culture flasks coated with 0.1 % w/v gelatine.
410 Endothelial cell growth medium-2 (EGM-2 MV Microvascular Endothelial Cell Growth Medium-2 BulletKit; Lonza;
411 CC-3202) was refreshed twice a week. Once a week, HUVECs were split at a 1:3 ratio. MSCs were cultured in cell
412 culture flasks coated with 0.1 % w/v gelatine. MSC medium (10% FCS, 1% pen/strep, 1% asap in alpha-MEM
413 (Gibco)) was refreshed twice a week. Once a week, MSCs were split at a 1:3 ratio. All cell cultures were kept in a
414 humidified atmosphere of 95% O₂ and 5% CO₂ at 37 °C.

415 **4.8 Chip seeding and culture**

416 Prior to cell seeding, all liquid around and inside the chips was removed and chips were dried at 37°C until cells were
417 prepared for seeding (~ 30 min). MCF10A, HUVECs, MSCs and MBOs were trypsinized into single cells and counted.
418 Cells were resuspended in their respective culture medium at different densities (7.5 M/mL, 15 M/mL, 30 M/mL, 60
419 M/mL for MCF10A; 20 M/mL for HUVECs) and injected into channels. Bioreactors were clamped closed and inserted
420 into PDMS inserts in 15 cm petri dishes, which were wrapped with parafilm. Multiwell plates were wrapped with
421 parafilm. Multiwell plates and petri dishes were inserted into the gel rotator and secured with the belt. Chips were
422 rotated at 37°C for 6 hours, rotating by 90° every 10 minutes. Subsequently, warm culture medium was added around
423 the chips but not covering the top of the chip to prevent media from flushing freshly seeded cells out of the channel.
424 Chips were seeded a second time two days later. From day three after the second seeding, culture medium was not
425 only refreshed twice a week but also freshly injected into the channels twice a day if no perfusion was applied.

426 **4.9 Immunofluorescent stainings and confocal imaging**

427 Stainings were performed as previously described⁵². Briefly, chips were fixed in cold PFA (4% w/v) for 1.5 h on a
428 rocker at 4°C. Samples were washed with PBT (PBS + 0.1 % w/v Tween20) and kept in PBT until further processed.
429 Before staining, samples were washed in WB2 (1 L PBS + 1 mL of Triton X-100 + 2 mL of 10% (w/v) SDS + 2 g
430 BSA) for 30 min at 4°C. Epithelial channels were stained for rabbit-anti-cytokeratin-14 (1:1000, Biolegend; 905301),
431 mouse-anti-cytokeratin-8/18 (1:500; Abcam; ab17139), and rat-anti-E-cadherin (1:200; Thermo Fisher; 13-1900) in
432 WB2 overnight. The next day, samples were washed 3x for 1.5 h in WB2. Samples were stained for DAPI (1:1000;
433 Thermo Fisher Scientific Invitrogen™ D1306), Phalloidin-Atto700 (1:200; SigmaAldrich 79286-10NMOL) and
434 donkey-anti-mouse-AF555 (1:200, Thermo Fisher Scientific; A31570), donkey -anti-rabbit-AF647 (Thermo Fisher
435 Scientific; A31573) and donkey-anti-rat-AF594 (Thermo Fisher Scientific; A21209) over night at 4°C. Endothelial
436 channels were further stained for CD31-AF488 (1:200; Biolegend; 102513). The next day samples were washed 3x
437 1.5 h in WB2, vibratome cut into 350 µm slices and mounted onto thin glass slides. Imaging was executed on a Leica
438 Stellaris confocal microscope using 25X magnification. Chips were evaluated for cell coverage and location of the
439 markers of interest.

440 **4.10 Assessment of cell coverage**

441 Using segmentation in Imaris imaging software 10.1 (Oxford Instruments) we generated a mask of the outline of the
442 channel through manual segmentation and of the cells through intensity-based segmentation. To account for possible
443 inaccuracies in manual segmentation, we expanded the channel mask inwards and outwards. Masked data was
444 imported to python. From the center point (start point) of the channel we computationally approached every point on
445 the outer circumference of the channel (target point) checking for positive values in the cell mask. Once a positive
446 value was found, this target point was considered covered. Every point on that outer circumference was thereby
447 classified into cell-covered and not cell-covered and the percentage of cells covering the channel surface was
448 calculated from the total amount of target points (Suppl.Fig.2B). The script to calculate channel coverage can be found
449 in the OSF repository³⁴.

450 **4.11 Perfusion startup**

451 To ensure wiggle-free perfused culture, we designed, and 3D printed a perfusion tray, holding the media bottle,
452 bioreactor and tubing in place. The tray holds a 5.5 cm glass bottle and an 8 cm petri dish. Further, clips with different
453 diameter indentations were printed that slide onto triangular extrusions to hold different sizes of tubing in place.
454 Additionally, four pins were printed to secure the tubing on the pumps side. All non-3D-printed components were
455 autoclaved, ahead of perfusion experiments. 3D printed components were cleaned with ethanol and allowed to air dry.
456 The setup was assembled and perfused with PBS to check for leaks. Subsequently, the setup was flushed with
457 Advanced DMEM supplemented with 5 % v/v P/S, 5 % v/v Glutamax and 5 % v/v HEPES (F+++) to prime all tubings
458 and connectors. F+++ was then replaced by the desired culture media. For perfused culture of endothelial channels,
459 MSC and HUVEC medium were mixed at a 1:1 ratio.

460 Chips were inserted into the bioreactor and care was taken to properly align the lid with help of the guide extrusions.
461 Soft tubing (TackleShop.nl B.V; Cresta Superstretch Silicone Tube 1m 0.4mm) was inserted into the channel through
462 the holes in the lid until the resistance of the channel curvature could be felt. Suction and pumping were applied at the
463 same time to facilitate smooth perfusion. Perfusion was started at the lowest possible setting of our pump setup (80
464 $\mu\text{L/h}$) and gradually increased over the coming days, when cells were found to withstand the shear stress. Chips were
465 perfused for up to three weeks. Media was refreshed weekly.

466 **4.12 Evaluation of barrier function using FITC-Inulin**

467 Cell-free chips, cellular chips that were cultured under static culture conditions and cellular chips that were cultured
468 under perfused conditions were injected with FITC-Inulin (Merck, F3272-1G). Using the Leica Thunder imaging
469 system time lapses of the FITC signal were recorded at 2 min intervals. Imaging data was segmented manually to
470 generate a mask of the channel and the increase of FITC signal outside the boundaries of the channel was quantified
471 over time using a python analysis script³⁴ (Suppl.Fig.2E).

472 **4.13 Assessment of basal-luminal cellular organization**

473 Using segmentation in Imaris imaging software we generated a mask of the outline of the channel through manual
474 segmentation and of the cells positive for K8/18 and K14 through intensity-based segmentation. To account for
475 possible inaccuracies in manual segmentation we expanded the channel mask inwards and outwards. Masked data was
476 imported to python. From the center point (start point) of the channel we computationally approached every point on
477 the outer circumference of the channel (target point) checking for positive values in the two cell masks. If the first
478 match found in the K8/18 mask, this circumference point was considered *covered by a luminal cell first*. The
479 percentage of circumference points covered by luminal cells was calculated. Further, the percentage of circumference
480 points for which first a signal from the K8/18 mask was obtained followed by a signal from the K14 mask was
481 calculated and named *Correct basal luminal organization* (Suppl.Fig.1C). The script to calculate channel coverage
482 can be found in the OSF repository³⁴.

483 **4.14 Assessment of cell alignment**

484 Cells covering the channel surface were segmented using intensity-based segmentation in Imaris and the ratio of each
485 cells' bounding box in Z- and Y-direction was calculated. When the bounding box was longer in Z-direction than in
486 Y-direction, it was considered longitudinally aligned (Suppl.Fig.2D). Alignment of cells was quantified using a
487 custom R script which is free to download in our OSF repository³⁴.

488 **4.15 Statistical analysis**

489 Results were reported as mean \pm standard deviation. Statistical analysis was performed in GraphPad Prism 9.
490 Comparisons between experimental conditions was assessed via One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple

491 comparisons test. For comparison of less than three groups unpaired parametric t test or Welch’s t test were performed.
492 Results were considered significant with a p-value < 0.05.

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499 500 **6. Disclosures**

501 R.L. is scientific advisor for Readily3D, which did not participate in or bias the work. The other authors declare no
502 competing interests.

503 **7. Data availability**

504 All supplementary data as well as analysis pipelines can be found in our open science repository under the following
505 URL: https://osf.io/gtqf4/?view_only=d22b7cc53c57486198835443d7d6e006

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644 Figure 1: Chip design considerations and printing quality. (a) Schematic of molding approach. (b) Schematic
645 illustration and fluorescent image of issue with cells floating out of the chip, represented by fluorescent beads. Scale
646 bar = 2 mm. (c) Schematic and bright-field (BF) image of air bubbles (red arrows) arising from inserting plug. Scale
647 bar = 1 mm. (d) Schematic and fluorescent image of U-shaped chip designs which allows for more reliable cell seeding
648 here illustrated by the injection of fluorescent beads. Scale bar = 2 mm. (e) Percentage deviations of the printed chip
649 from original CAD model. (f) Predicted light intensity normalized to the median light intensity over the whole 3D
650 model. (g) Percentage deviation of printed chip zoom in showing narrowing of the channel at the inlets. (h) Cross
651 section of predicted light intensity at the channel inlet. (i-k) Printing accuracy for X, Y and Z coordinates.

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654 Figure 2: Seeding setup and optimization. (a) Schematic of rotation setup. (b) Fluorescent images of chips seeded with
655 (left) and without (right) rotation. (c) Percentage of the channel surface covered by cells with and without rotation. (d)
656 Channels seeded with MCF10A with different coatings. (e) Percentage of the channels (length= 9 mm diameter = 1
657 mm) covered with cells with different cell coatings. (f) Channels seeded with different densities of MCF10A and (g)
658 Percentage channel coverage. (h) Channels seeded with HUVECs at 20 M cells/mL with different coatings. (i) Channel
659 coverage of HUVECs with different coatings. Scale bars = 100 μ m. Images were taken one week after cell seeding.
660 Differences in cell coverage according to One-way ANOVA were not significant due to sample size unless indicated
661 otherwise (* for $p < 0.05$).

663 Figure 3 Bioreactor setup. (a) Schematic of bioreactor parts and functions. (b) 3D printed bioreactor. (c) CNC
664 machined bioreactor. (d) Perfusion setup. Zoom in: Tubing clips.

666 Figure 4: Influence of perfusion on cellular organization of mammary epithelial cells. (a) Percentage expansion
667 patterns of channels under perfusion. (b) Plot of the channel edges at maximum and minimum distance. (c) BF images
668 of perfused and non-perfused channels showing cell invasion into the surrounding tissue for perfused chips as assessed
669 through measurements in Fiji. Scale bar = 500 μm . (d) FITC-Inulin perfusion into seeded channels and FITC
670 quantification outside the channel boundaries over time, as well as (e) Quantification of the area under the curve
671 outside of the channel boundaries, demonstrating epithelial barrier function under perfusion. Scale bar = 500 μm . (f)
672 Immunofluorescent images of non- perfused and perfused chips (g). Scale bar = 100 μm . (h) Percentage of cells lining
673 the inner edge of the duct that are K8/18 positive. (i) Percentage of cells lining the duct for which the inner layer is
674 K8/18 positive and is followed by K14 positive cells. Data was acquired after two weeks of perfusion. Differences
675 between culture conditions were not statistically significant due to sample size unless indicated otherwise (* for $p <$
676 0.05) as calculated through One-way ANOVA (e) and unpaired t-test (h,i).

678 Figure 5: Strategies to improve model maturation. (a) Fluorescent images of chips seeded with MCF10A or HUVECs
679 displaying cellular alignment along the channels circumference. Scale bar = 100 μm (b) Schematic and BF images of
680 chip printed in vertical orientation. Scale bar = 250 μm . (c) Schematic and BF images of chip printed in horizontal
681 orientation. Scale bar = 250 μm . (d) Fluorescent images of horizontally printed chips seeded with MCF10A or
682 HUVECs displaying longitudinal cell alignment. Scale bar = 100 μm . (e) Quantification of cell alignment by print
683 orientation. (f) Nominal comparison of horizontally printed chip indicating reduced channel diameters along
684 longitudinal axis. (g) Computed light intensities over the model when printed horizontally indicating high light
685 accumulation within horizontally printed part of the duct. (h) Schematic, BF images (i) and fluorescent images (j) of
686 chip containing an epithelial duct with lobular structures. Scale bar = 1 mm. (k) Fluorescent image showing MCF10A
687 invasion from the lobular structures (k). Scale bar = 200 μm (l) m) Schematic of chip with
688 two channels of 200 μm distance. Scale bar = 200 μm . (n) Fluorescent images of 2-channel chip demonstrating the
689 separate culture of these two cell types. Scale bar = 200 μm . Statistical significance of differences between vertically
690 and horizontally printed chips was assessed using Welch's t-test (** for $p < 0.01$; * for $p < 0.05$).
691

693 Supplementary Figure 1 3D imaging-based analysis pipelines presented in this technical note. (a) 3D reconstructions
694 from light-sheet imaging were compared to original CAD models in CloudCompare. A custom R script was used to
695 calculate percentage deviations and to backproject into the 3D model. (b) A custom python script was used to identify
696 circumference points on the outer edge of the channel and identify cells between the inner and outer edge covering
697 the duct surface. (c) The python script was adapted to identify correct basal-luminal organization. (d) Using Y and Z
698 bounding box dimensions of single segmented cells, circumferentially and longitudinally aligned cells were identified
699 for different print orientations using a custom R script. (e) Manual segmentation was used to create a mask of the
700 FITC-Inulin injected channel. The masked data and FITC signal was spatially quantified using a custom python script
701 and normalized to the maximum intensity at $t = 0$.

703 Supplementary Figure 2 (a) Detailed view and part description of rotation device. (b) BF images of different MCF10A
 704 seeding densities acquired three days after the first or second seeding respectively. Red circles indicating gaps in the
 705 cell layer, yellow circles indicating cell aggregation in the lumen of the channel. (c) BF images of MCF10A seeded
 706 onto different coatings. Scale bars = 500 μm .

a)

707
 708 Supplementary Figure 3 (a) Quantification of MCF10A invasion distance from the ductal and lobular channel surface
 709 measured in Fiji. Invasion distance of printed chips was assessed after one week of culture. Statistical significance of
 710 differences in cell invasion depth was assessed using an unpaired t-test (**** for $p < 0.0001$; *** for $p < 0.001$; **
 711 for $p < 0.01$; * for $p < 0.05$).

a)

b)

c)

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713 Supplementary Figure 4 (a) Fluorescence image of a cross-section of a printed chip with encapsulated human MSCs
714 (green). Scale bar = 1 mm. (b) Viability of human MSCs encapsulated in gel during printing on day 1, 7 and 14 after
715 printing respectively in MSC or MCF10A media. (c) Hydrogel stiffness of printed disc structures containing human
716 MSCs on day 1, 7 and 14 after printing, respectively.

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